

Mekong

The annual cycle of life on the Mekong River is characterised by the Monsoon climate system causing distinct seasons. The wet season brings extensive flooding into the delta and the Great Lake Tonlé Sap, supporting rice cultivation and the spawning of fish feeding in the floodplains. Ample water flowing in the rivers offers efficient waterborne transport of goods and population. The onset of the dry season sees dramatic decline in water levels, while the absence of rain makes land transport optimal. As fish migrate upstream or take refuge in the deep pools of the river, fishermen take advantage of these migrations to catch them as they leave or as they become trapped in receding waters. Large scale seasonal migration occurs at this time, when people from all over the country take part in the *prahok* – Khmer fish paste – season, which usually begins in January. These migrations yield one of the largest catches of inland fisheries around the world. As the dry season presses on, most of the tropical rivers no longer support navigation, and transport becomes increasingly difficult by hot and dry months of April and May. The rains start again to wet the ground in June, and as the rivers swell, the fish are flushed out of their refuge and begin migration once again to the floodplains. Such is the pulse of the Lower Mekong River Basin in Cambodia and Southern Laos.

This, the first of a set of diachronic maps, attempts to provide an overview of the fluvial cultural landscape of the Mekong River basin with an emphasis on the Khmer empire of Angkor and the historical ecology of the basin. The extent of river navigability for economic purposes is determined by the location of *kampongs*, which ancient epigraphy described as crossing points, landing places and/or river ports. The *kampongs* marked here are from 19th and 20th century maps, reflecting traditional use of space with local watercraft. We can see that kampongs were often strategically placed close to river confluences, fishing grounds, deep pools, and major settlements. Laterite bridges from the Angkor period are also important markers in the landscape, as they impeded river travel and could be used as control points by the state. The bridges were placed where road network was given precedence over river transport. The largest of the Angkorian bridges, *Spean Praptos*, is pictured. Rapids along the Mekong river had a similar effect working as transitional points for river trade.

During the Angkor period, regional transport networks were complemented by an extensive system of canals used by boats, and reservoirs of varied sizes called *Baray*, many of which were used to water traction animals used for land transport. Profound knowledge of water management is one of the key characteristics of Angkorian culture. Their close relationship with water is also evident in the rich nautical iconography found in the temples.

Historical Ecology

Main data source used in this study is Walker, Verónica, The Fluvial Cultural Landscape of Angkor, University of Oxford, 2016. Map design by Marko Kallias and Verónica Walker. Numerous data sources were used to compile the information. In addition to the main document, we used historical maps by D. Harmand (1876), E. Garnier (1883), A. Perre (1901), L. de Lajoussière (1901), 1911), Service géographique de l'Indochine (1898), and Office local du tourisme au Cambodge (1923) to locate the historical kampongs marked. We also used modern map sources - Google Maps, OpenStreetMap, and a paper road map published by Cambodia Airways - for additional kampongs. Locations for historical sites in the Mekong basin and upstream of Mekong from Khone Falls were approximated from Lorrillard (2014). The Angkor era roads and bridges were digitised and traced through satellite imagery and maps by B. Bruguier (2000), and M. Hendrickson (2007, 2010). The Angkor hydraulic system shown in the inset map was traced using information from M. Kamura (2009). Deep pool locations were sourced from the Mekong River Commission, and fishing lots approximated from maps published by the UN Food and Agriculture Organisation. The floodplain is derived from MERIT Hydro 30-meter resolution Digital Elevation Model. Floodplain maximum extent and flood duration downstream from Kratie were derived from hydrodynamic modelling. Upstream from Kratie, maximum extent is approximately digitised from 100-year flood simulations by Dartmouth Flood Observatory. The photo showing Bayon nautical scene is by Atandajati / Wikimedia Commons (CC BY 2.0). Photo of Preah Khan Baray is by Miguel Vicente Martínez Juan / Flickr (CC BY-NC 2.0) This is version 1, published on 2020.06.29. If used in publications, please cite DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3827019.